

Iodometric Estimation of Formates by Oxidation with Iodine

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A new procedure is described for the volumetric determination of formate ion, based on its oxidation by iodine solution. The hydriodic acid liberated during oxidation is estimated by a standard potassium iodate solution. The procedure is applicable to neutral formate solutions containing 30 to 90 mg. of formic acid with a precision of 1% or more. The interference caused by the salts of other organic acids and organic substances has also been studied.

Fuchs (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 78, 125), Oldeman (*Pharm. Weekblad.*, 1931, 68, 379), and Bose (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 320) estimated neutral formates by oxidation with mercuric chloride solution and made subsequent determination of the acid produced during oxidation. The acidimetric estimation is interfered by carbon dioxide liberated during oxidation. Verma and Pcse (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 47) volumetrically estimated the calomel produced by Andrew's method. The latter procedure is free from any interference caused by carbon dioxide. In the present method a formate solution is heated with an excess of iodine solution for a considerable time when it is oxidised by iodine according to the equation :

According to Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 726) the reaction occurs even at ordinary temperature with a measurable velocity. The hydrogen ions formed as a product of the change greatly retard the reaction. To obviate this Dhar used an excess of sodium acetate whereby the reaction became regular for kinetic study.

The reaction was found bimolecular, depending on the concentrations of formate ion and iodine. Iodide ion was also found to retard this oxidation reaction. In the present procedure potassium iodate solution was added to remove hydrogen ions, thus avoiding the use of a buffer, and iodine solution was prepared by adding minimum amount of KI to keep the iodide concentration low. The reaction was carried out at an elevated temperature (60-100°) and the hydriodic acid produced was estimated by adding an excess of a standard iodate solution. The reaction takes place in accordance with the equation :

Later the residual potassium iodate was estimated by treating with an excess of H_2SO_4 and titrating the liberated iodine with a standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The amount of potassium iodate consumed affords the hydriodic acid liberated during the reaction and thus the amount of formate present is indirectly evaluated. ($6\text{HCOOH} \equiv 6\text{HI} \equiv \text{KIO}_3 \equiv 3\text{I}_2 \equiv 6\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$).

1 c.c. of *M*/80- KIO_3 solution = 3.45 mg. of formic acid.

1 c.c. of *N*/10 sodium thiosulphate solution = 4.6 mg. of formic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium thiosulphate, iodine, and starch were of A.R. quality ; potassium iodate was of Merck's variety and sodium formate was of B.D.H. A standard solution (0.025 *M*) of potassium iodate was prepared by dissolving 5.351 g. of the salt, dried at 120° for 1 hour, in 1 litre of water. Standard solutions of sodium formate were prepared by dissolving different amounts of the salt after drying at 100° for 1 hour.

The other solutions prepared were 0.5*N* and 0.025*N* sodium thiosulphate, 0.4*N* iodine (containing 75 g. of potassium iodide per litre), and 1% aqueous starch. *M*/80-KIO₃ solution was prepared by diluting the *M*/40 solution.

Procedure.—To a neutral solution (10 to 20 c.c.) of formate containing about 30 to 90 mg. of formic acid, taken in a 250 c.c. conical flask, a standard solution of potassium iodate was added in a known excess. 0.4*N* Iodine solution (10 c.c.) was also introduced in the flask and the total volume was made to 40 c.c. The flask was kept immersed in an electrical water bath, containing water at 25°, and weighted by encircling its lower portion by a band of lead. About two third of the flask was under water. The rate of heating the bath was so adjusted that 10 to 12 minutes were required to start boiling. The flask was kept in boiling water for 30 minutes after the start of boiling so that the total period of heating was 40 minutes. The flask was then taken out and cooled under tap. A 0.5*N* sodium thiosulphate solution was gradually added from a burette till the solution in the flask was faint yellow. At this stage 1 c.c. of starch solution was added and the iodine was precisely neutralised with *N*/40 thiosulphate solution. The contents of the flask were acidified by adding about 2c.c. of 1*N*-H₂SO₄; the liberated iodine was titrated with a standard thiosulphate solution. A blank was also carried out in exactly similar manner except for the addition of the formate solution. The difference between two hypo readings gave iodate consumed in terms of hypo equivalent. The results for the evaluation of different formate solutions are recorded in Table I. All the estimations were carried out in duplicate.

TABLE I

Formic acid	{	Present (mg.)	..	..	92.0	82.8	69.0	55.2	46.0	32.2
		Found (mg.)	..	..	92.3	83.5	69.6	55.4	46.3	32.0
		%Error	..	..	0.4	1.0	0.9	0.4	0.7	-0.6

Effect of change in the time of heating, in the amount of water, and in the concentration of iodine solution was studied. The results are recorded in Tables II, III, and IV respectively.

TABLE II

Effect of change in the period of boiling.

(10 c.c. of *M*/10 formate solution+20 c.c. of *M*/80-KIO₃ solution+10c.c. of 0.4*N* iodine solution)

Time after start of boiling.	Total period of heating.	Formic acid.		%Error.
		Present.	Found.	
10 mins.	22 mins.	46.0 mg.	46.4 mg.	+0.9
20	32	..	46.4	+0.9
28 (recommended)	40	..	46.1	+0.3
40	52	..	46.1	+0.3
60	72	..	46.0	±0.0
90	102	..	46.1	+0.3

Total time of heating for 30 to 40 minutes was found suitable. It was found necessary to adjust the rate of heating in a way that the time required for boiling to start was about 10 to 12 minutes.

TABLE III

Effect of increase in the amount of water.

(10 c.c. of $M/10$ formate solution + different amounts of water + 20 c.c. of $M/80$ - KIO_3 solution + 10 c.c. of $0.4N$ - I_2 solution). Total time of heating = 40 mins.

Water added.	Total volume.	Formic acid.		%Error.
		Present.	Found.	
0.0 c.c.	40.0 c.c. (recommended)	46.0	46.1	+0.3
10.0	50.0	..	46.3	+0.7
20.0	60.0	..	46.8	+1.8
30.0	70.0	..	47.6	+3.6
40.0	80.0	..	48.0	+4.8
50.0	90.0	..	48.5	+5.3

Increase in the amount of water resulted in higher values for formate. Best results were obtained when the total volume was about 40 c.c.

TABLE IV

Effect of change in the concentration of iodine.

(10 c.c. of $M/10$ formate solution + 10 c.c. of $M/40$ - KIO_3 solution + different amounts of iodine solution). Total volume = 40 c.c. Total time of heating = 40 mins.

0.4N- I_2 soln. added.	Water added.	Formic acid.		%Error.
		Present.	Found.	
5.0 c.c.	15.0 c.c.	46.0 mg.	45.3 mg.	-1.5
7.5	12.5	..	46.2	+0.5
10.0 (recommended)	10.0	..	46.2	+0.5
12.5	7.5	..	46.4	+0.9
15.0	5.0	..	46.9	+2.0
20.0	0.0	..	48.3	+5.0

7.5 to 10 c.c. of $0.4N$ iodine solution proved suitable for 46 mg. of formic acid. For the estimation of formate solution containing 30 to 90 mg. of formic acid, 10 c.c. of $0.4N$ iodine solution was used.

Interference.—Table V shows the interference caused by salts of organic acids and other organic substances. Glucose, benzaldehyde, and sodium salicylate showed profound interference and all the iodate added was consumed while addition of borax resulted in low values for formate so that almost all the iodate remained unchanged. This is probably due to the buffering of hydrogen ions by this salt.

TABLE V

(10 c.c. of *M*/10 sodium formate + 20 c.c. of *M*/80-KIO₃ solution + substance + 10 c.c. of 0.4*N* iodine solution). Total time of heating = 40 mins. Sodium formate added = 68.0 mg.

Expt. No.	Substance added.	Sodium formate found.	%Error.
1.	EtOH (1 c.c.)	73.3 mg.	+ 8.0
2.	CCl ₄ ..	72.3	+ 6.5
3.	K-citrate (0.2 g.)	57.8	-15.5
4.	Ca-gluconate ..	72.9	+ 7.5
5.	.. lactate ..	73.6	+ 8.5
6.	.. butyrate ..	60.0	-12.0
7.	Formaldehyde ..	96.4	+42.6
8.	Acetaldehyde ..	79.4	+17.0
9.	Salicylaldehyde ..	87.7	+29.5
10.	Na-tartrate ..	67.5	- 0.7
11.	.. acetate (in equimol. conc.)	66.8	- 1.7
12.	.. malonate (containing 0.2 g. of acid)	64.3	- 5.5
13.	.. benzoate ..	72.8	+ 7.2
14.	.. adipate ..	45.4	-34.0
15.	.. fumarate ..	67.0	- 1.0
16.	.. maleate ..	14.3	-80.5
17.	.. malate ..	62.5	- 8.2
18.	.. phenylacetate ..	67.5	- 0.7
19.	.. aminoacetate ..	64.3	- 5.5
20.	.. propionate (equimol. proportion)	67.0	- 1.5

In the above procedure potassium iodate solution serves two purposes—estimation of hydriodic acid produced and removal of hydrogen ions. Addition of a buffer is not necessary. The disadvantage of the method lies in the interference caused by a large number of substances. Sodium acetate or propionate, if present in equimolar concentration, does not interfere much. In presence of large concentrations of these salts of homologues of formic acid, the method fails probably due to the buffering action of acetate and propionate ions, which prevent the hydriodic acid produced from reacting with potassium iodate. Hence this procedure is recommended for the estimation of neutral solutions of formates in absence of oxidisable impurities. The procedure being iodometric is simple and exhibits a sharp end point.

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